

Trace stripping voltammetric determination of quercetin at quercetin self-assembled monolayer (SAM)/carbon paste electrode

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Manuscript received online 09 January 2013, accepted 07 August 2013

Abstract : A new method was developed for determination quercetin (Qu) based on their adsorptive stripping voltammetric response at a carbon paste electrode (CPE) modified with a quercetin self-assembled monolayer (SAM). A stable quercetin modified electrode was prepared and its electrochemical behaviour was investigated voltammetrically. In 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 2.14) quercetin exhibits a sensitive anodic peak at around 0.55 V (vs SCE) at the SAMQu/CPE electrode. The stability of the quercetin SAM/carbon paste modified electrode is very good. The quercetin self-assembled monolayer is an effective surface for the oxidation of quercetin. Quercetin does not interfere with ascorbic acid at the modified electrode. After optimizing the parameters such as pH value, preconcentration time, and preconcentration potential, a novel electrochemical method is simple, fast, sensitive, and can used to determine quercetin with high accuracy. Under the optimal experimental conditions, the anodic peak current is linear with quercetin concentration in the range of 1.0 to 18.0 μM . The detection limit was evaluated to be 8.40×10^{-7} M quercetin ($r = 0.9997$).

Keywords : Quercetin, self-assembled monolayer, carbon paste electrode, adsorptive stripping, SAMQu/CPE electrode, detection limit.

Introduction

Quercetin (Qu) is a natural antioxidant present in the plant kingdom and the common human diets. It has various beneficial effects on human health due to their polyphenolic nature with radical-scavenging activity and metal-chelating properties. Various analytical methods have been reported for the determination of Qu. Liquid chromatograph^{1,2}, UV-Vis spectrophotometry^{3,4}, and mass spectrometry^{5,6} have been used to determine the presence of Qu and other flavones in plants. These techniques provide high sensitivity for the assay; yet, they also have disadvantages, as complexity of operation, reagent-consuming, and high cost. Since Qu contains phenolic hydroxyl groups which exhibit electroactivity at oxidation potential. Therefore, it is essential to develop rapid, simple and selective electrochemical method for the determination of quercetin. Quercetin was determined using stripping voltammetry at bare⁷ and nanocarbon tubes⁸⁻¹² carbon paste electrode. Recently, automated solid-phase extraction hyphenated to voltammetry was used for the determination of quercetin¹³.

Self assembled monolayers (SAMs) have been described as a spontaneous, coordinated chemical interaction of individual molecular building blocks to create a stable, highly ordered and densely packed single layer of molecules from a solution or a gas phase onto a substrate^{14,15}. Over the past two decades, SAMs have received extensive attention due to their stability, simple formation and potentiality of application in many fields such as sensor and biosensor construction studies¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and trace ion determination¹⁹⁻²².

In this study, a trace stripping voltammetric method for the determination of quercetin was developed using carbon paste electrode modified with quercetin self-assembled monolayer (SAM). Cyclic voltammetry experiments shows that the modified electrode is stable in 0.2 M phosphate buffer and it can be used as an electrochemical sensor for determination of Qu.

Experimental

Material and methods :

Electrochemical experiments were performed on a EG

& G Electrochemical system with a conventional three-electrode cell. A modified carbon paste electrode with quercetin self-assembled monolayer (SAM) serves as working electrode, a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and a platinum wire serve as reference and auxiliary electrodes, respectively. All the chemical reagents used for solutions were reagent grade from Merck and used as received. Deionized water was used to prepare buffer and reagent solutions. The supporting electrolyte used in all the experiments was 0.2 M phosphate buffer solutions. All solutions were freshly prepared just before use with deionized water.

Preparation of SAMQu/CPE modified electrode :

The self assembled monolayers quercetin-modified electrode, SAMQu/CPE, was prepared by deposition of quercetin on immersion of the carbon paste electrode (CPE) in a 0.2 M phosphate buffer solution containing quercetin for the appropriate deposition time. The effect of various experimental variables on the deposition of quercetin was investigated to optimize the modification. Monolayer was formed by the self-assembling technique on the carbon paste electrode. Upon removal the modified electrode from the deposition solution, it was thoroughly rinsed with water to remove the physically adsorbed species. During this stage, a deposited layer of quercetin is bound to the sur-

face of the carbon paste electrode.

Results and discussion

Modification of electrode :

The effect of various experimental variables on the deposition of quercetin was investigated to optimize the modification. Effect of the deposition potential on the surface coverage was investigated by fixing switching potential at 0.7 volt and changing the anodic deposition potential from 0.0 to 0.4 volt. Fig. 1 displays the variation of the anodic peak current, i_p , with deposition potential. It is seen that at 0.0 V the relation has a maximum current value. Thus, the favorable coverage was obtained when the anodic deposition potential is set to 0.0. The variation of the surface coverage as a function of quercetin solution pH shows that acidic solution, pH 2.14, is more favorable for the modification than neutral or alkaline media. Therefore pH value of 2.14 was selected as the optimal pH. Dependence of the surface coverage on the deposition time, immersion time, reveals that the favorable modification occurs at 240 s, *c.f.* Fig. 2. Finally, the effect of quercetin concentration on the surface coverage indicates that the best coverage was obtained when the modification was carried out in 2.5 μ M quercetin solution. Therefore, sweeping of potential between 0.0

Fig. 1. The relationship between the peak current i_p versus deposition potential on 2.5 μ M quercetin in 0.2 M phosphate buffer, pH 2.14, at scan rate of 30 mV/s.

Fig. 2. The relationship between the peak current i_p versus deposition time, 2.5 μM quercetin in 0.2 M phosphate buffer, pH 2.14, at scan rate of 30 mV/s.

and 0.7 V, pH 2.14, 2.5 μM quercetin and 250 s are selected as optimal conditions for modification of the electrode and used in all subsequent studies.

Adsorption stripping voltammetric determination of quercetin :

For adsorption stripping voltammetric determination of quercetin, the optimum stripping parameters such as preconcentration time, preconcentration potential and pH were investigated. Effect of preconcentration potential on stripping response of SAM modified electrode towards Qu was carried out on varying the potential from 0.0 to 0.30 V. On changing preconcentration potential, the peak current increases gradually to a maximum at 0.15 V. This means that a more positive potential is favorable to the accumulation of quercetin. Thus, optimum preconcentration potential was applied at 0.15 V. The effect of preconcentration time on the magnitude of the stripping peak current was examined in the range of 25–300 s. Preconcentration time is favoured at 180 s. The influences of the pH of quercetin solutions during the preconcentration step on the stripping peak current was also examined. The variation of the stripping peak current as a function of quercetin solution pH shows that acidic solution, pH 2.14, is more favorable for accumu-

lation of Qu on the subject electrode than neutral or alkaline media. Therefore pH value of 2.14 was selected as the optimal. In conclusion, preconcentration potential of 0.15 V, preconcentration time of 250 s, and pH 2.14 were selected as the optimal pH conditions for adsorptive stripping voltammetric determination of quercetin.

In order to test the feasibility of this method for quercetin determination, the relationship between the adsorptive stripping peak current and quercetin concentration is studied.

Under the optimal conditions, the quercetin self-assembled monolayer/carbon paste electrode, SAMQu/CPE, offers well defined Qu concentration dependence. Fig. 3 displays a linear sweep voltammograms recorded following successive increments in Qu concentration between 1.0 to 18.0 μM . A well-defined anodic stripping LSV wave is observed. Fig. 4 represent the calibration plot for the entire concentration range of investigation. A linear dependence between stripping peak current and Qu concentration is observed with a regression coefficient of 0.9997, *c.f.* Fig. 4. The linear least squares equation is represented as follows :

$$i_p \text{ (nA)} = 176.14 + 57.45 c_{\text{Qu}} \text{ (\mu M)} \quad r = 0.9997$$

The detection limit for quercetin is $8.40 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$ (S/N = 3).

Fig. 3. Typical LSV of different concentrations of quercetin on SAMQu/CPE in pH 2.14 phosphate buffer at scan rate of 30 mV/s.

Fig. 4. Calibration curve of quercetin at the SAMQu/CPE. Scan rate of 30 mV/s, accumulation time of 180 s, accumulation potential of 0.15 V and pH 2.14.

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